

ASPECTS OF THE USAGE OF METAPHORS IN THE LYRICS OF POET K. KARIMOV

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Abstract. *We decided to dwell on the service and usage aspects of metaphors in the creation of an artistic image in Karakalpak lyrics, including the work of the poet K. Karimov in this article.*

Keywords: *lyrics, artistic image, poetics, tropes, metaphor.*

In literature, metaphors, like all tropes are used in order to clearly and effectively reflect objects and events. Metaphor is a figurative usage of the word in a different sense than its basic meaning. The metaphor is based on the conditionality of similarity between objects. In a metaphor, one object is repeatedly named with the name of another object, and on this basis the figurativeness of the word appears. Many literary scholars have expressed their scientific opinion about this. [1.] An artistic work is considered to be an artistic embodiment of life, society, nature and events in the spiritual world of a person, and metaphor is of great importance in ensuring the beauty of this work and enriching its content. Appropriate metaphors can fully and beautifully convey the creator's intention, ideas, and opinions. For example, we have paid attention to the poet's song "Ótken ásir" ("The Last Century"):

Ol taman soqpaqlar endi kómilgen,
Heshkimge boysınbas waqıt qorǵanı,
Atızına ótmish urıǵı sebilgen
Tariyxqa aylanıp barar. Bolǵanı. [2:12]

In these lines, metaphors such as "fort of time" and "seed of the past" are given. We know that the fortress protects people, society, and the state from any external threats. It must therefore be very strong. We can understand that time is not subservient to his will and cannot be broken by the name of the "fortress of time" in the lyrics of the song. At the same time, we can understand the following meaning from the metaphor "seed of the past". We know that the seed is the variety, the grain, and the past is the old times, the past day, the events. The seeds of the past that are sown in our fields are our dreams, good and bad days, happy and sad times. They may now linger in our memories as ghostly imagination.

Poet K. Karimov makes appropriate use of metaphors used in common spoken and written poetry in constructing his feelings in a figurative sense, in revealing the lyrical content. During the study of K. Karimov's lyrics, we saw the effective usage of "foot", "flower", "liver", "nightingale", "swan", "sprout" and other metaphors characteristic of the language of poetry.

In K. Karimov's songs, the metaphor "liver" is skillfully used to convey the feelings, opinions, various social and natural events, and human feelings towards his country.

Dúnya gezip, teńiz kóllerdi kórdim,
Bawırı biypayan shóllerdi kórdim.
Nurǵa talpınıwshı ellerdi kórdim,
Ózińnen aǵlasın kórmedim Watan!

...Kimdur ol – qus tilin bilgen?
Sóz ishqında bawrını tilgen.

Also, the metaphor of "flower" is rarely used in the poet's lyrics:

...Búgin shadlan! Húrseń, gárezsiz elseń,

Aziya kóksinde ájayıp gúlseń. [2:78]

These lines of the poet are taken from the poem “Watan qasıydası” (“Ode to the Fatherland”) and he compares his country, his homeland, Uzbekistan, to a wonderful, beautiful flower rising on the Asian continent. The reason is that any poet or writer uses the most precious words to describe his country, his motherland. He paints them with different images and tries to deliver them.

...Meyli teńiz sheginse de,
Biz heshqashan sheginbeymiz!
Gúldey jaynap tuwǵan jerde,
Miyet penen gúl dónemiz. [2:137]

Here, the poet tried to give the meaning that we will achieve good days by working hard and still flourish by using the metaphor “we will bloom”.

At the same time, in the poet’s lyrics, one of the metaphors characteristics of the traditional, common language of the people is that we can also see metaphors related to the metaphor of the muscles of the human body:

Sóz ummanı hóktem dargası,
Áwladlardıń zor zamanlası,
Bir sıyqırlı júziktıń qasım -
Kim ol? – deseń, Nawayı háziret.
...Quladı million jıl kókti tiregen,
Jerdiń naq kindigi mángilik tawlar.

...Tepseń soqpaq ayaǵı bette,
Terbeledi bir túp qaraǵay.

...Meniń saǵan qádem qoyǵanım keshe,
Qarasam sap tartqan kárwanlar neshe. [2:132]

In the lines of this song, metaphors such as “eyebrow of the ring”, “navel of the earth”, “foot of the trail”, “caravan” are used, which served to convey the idea in a more artistic way.

If the inner spiritual world of the poet is rich, wide and deep, his lyrics will be folkloric. Such qualities of K. Karimov’s lyrics are also reflected in the metaphors used in it. The poet achieves a clear and concise description of some aspects and signs of the things they are describing with the help of metaphors. During the study of K. Karimov’s lyrics, we realized that there are also metaphors that are unique to the poet’s poetry.

We can see that the poet used metaphors appropriately in reflecting the philosophy of life based on the reality of life. For example, in his song “Táwekel qayıǵı” (“Risk Boat”) the following lines are quoted:

Táwekel qayıǵına mingen bendeniń,
Sabır qılmaqtan joq ózge sharası,
Qutırǵan dawıllar kernep jelqomın,
Jutsam deydi ot penen suw arası. [2:6]

The name of the song itself is a metaphor. Taking a risk is a word that can be used when people start their work with suspicion when starting something. Risk is a prediction. That is why proverbs such as “A risk-taker finishes his work till a thinker thinks” or “God is afraid of a risk-taker” are common among the people. A boat is an item used for river crossing or fishing. It would be correct if it remained in this sense, but the poet gave it a figurative meaning. “Risk boat” here is a suspicion, a prediction, that is, something that will happen or not.

Poet K. Karimov very skillfully used unique metaphors in his poetry. Through them, we can understand that the poet has his own path, that his creativity is not like anyone else's. We can see one of the unique metaphors in the following "Lám boldi" ("Wet eyes") song:

Bizdi bul pániyge taslap ketkenler,
Yadım dápterine bir-bir jám boldı. [2:18]

The metaphor of "memory copybook" is used here. The compared object is a person's thoughts, memory, and a similar object is a notebook. We can compare this metaphor to a personal diary of a person, in which people write down their best and worst moments, events that are sealed in their memory, and secrets that they cannot tell anyone else. Through these lines, the poet wanted to say that the people who were closest to him had left him and that he was remembering them.

At the same time, in the poet's poetry, we can see the presence of metaphors, the method of metaphorical representation, which completely carries the lines of the poem. For example, in the poem "Joǵalǵan pursat" ("Lost Opportunity") we can see the use of metaphor in three lines of the same song:

Kimlerdiń qolına tústiń naq bolıp,
Yaki ırǵaldıń ba gózzal baǵ bolıp,
Kárimtekli shashlarıma aq bolıp,
Qoǵan óziń be ediń, joǵalǵan pursat. [2:4]

The poet used metaphors such as "in cash", "in garden", "in white" in these lines. Here, he equated the lost opportunity with cash, a beautiful garden, and white hair.

In conclusion, metaphors are used very effectively and appropriately in the lyrics of the poet K. Karimov. He skillfully uses metaphors to express his reactions to social and political events, to express his reactions to natural phenomena, and to clearly reflect the spiritual forgiveness of the lyrical hero.

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